

The Role of Women's Rights in Authoritarian Entrenchment and Democratic Backsliding

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In recent years, both democratic and authoritarian incumbents have increasingly instrumentalized women's rights to consolidate their power. Applying a gender lens provides critical insights into how both co-optation and suppression of women's rights contribute to authoritarian entrenchment *and* democratic erosion in various global contexts, including in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA).

Authoritarian regimes frequently utilize women's rights reforms as a strategic tool to obscure their undemocratic practices. Under Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman, Saudi Arabia exemplifies this approach by implementing high-profile reforms such as lifting the ban on women driving and easing male guardianship requirements. These measures have portrayed Saudi Arabia as a reform-oriented nation to the international community. However, this image of progress masks a troubling reality, as Saudi women continue to face systemic discrimination and restrictions (Al-Rasheed 2021; Allam 2024). Activists advocating for more substantive reforms have faced harassment, arrest, and detention. By leveraging its publicized initiatives and reforms, the Saudi government has managed to preserve its authoritarian control and deflect

attention away from its ongoing human rights abuses.

Similarly, in Algeria, gender-based reforms were initially celebrated as a sign of democratic progress, with electoral gender quotas receiving praise from prominent international actors. However, after President Bouteflika was removed from power, these quotas were significantly rolled back, reducing women's representation in parliament from 26% to just 8% in 2021 (Marwane 2021). This reversal underscores how gender reforms in non-democratic contexts can be vulnerable to rollback, revealing the superficial nature of such reforms when they are not supported by broader democratic values and widespread public backing (Noh 2024; Noh, Grewal, and Kilavuz 2024).

In, more or less, democratic contexts, leaders have also manipulated women's rights policies to strengthen their rule while eroding democratic norms. Turkey's Recep Tayyip Erdoğan, Hungary's Viktor Orbán, and Brazil's Jair Bolsonaro have all adopted policies that undermine women's rights to galvanize conservative support (e.g., Çavdar 2024). These leaders have restricted reproductive rights and framed their actions as defending traditional family values, all while simultaneously

attacking feminist movements and reducing support for gender equality initiatives (Çavdar and Yaşar 2019). This suppression of women's rights has consistently been accompanied by broader democratic backsliding, such as threatening judicial independence, curbing press freedom, and suppressing dissent.

In Iraq, recent developments further illustrate how the manipulation of women's rights can reflect broader authoritarian tendencies and democratic erosion. Despite significant gains in women's activism and political representation, particularly during the 2019-2020 Tashreen protests and the 2021 federal elections, recent political maneuvers have threatened these advances. Conservative Islamist groups have resisted reforms and sought to decentralize the personal status law, likely legalizing child marriage and eroding women's rights—all while intensifying sectarian identity (Alshamary 2024). This politicization of women's rights, framed as a rejection of foreign or anti-Islamic values, highlights how gender reforms can be exploited to consolidate power and resist democratic changes in Iraq.

The examples provided underscore the importance of (i) understanding the instrumentalization of women and (ii) applying a gender lens to examine authoritarian consolidation and democratic backsliding. By examining how authoritarian regimes exploit gender reforms to project a superficial image of progress while simultaneously undermining democratic institutions and norms, we gain deeper insight into how autocrats maintain their dominance. In more democratic contexts, the suppression of women's rights can serve as an early warning of broader democratic decline, signaling deeper structural issues in governance and civil liberties. ♦

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